

Adjustment of the Geoelectric Model for a Ground Electrode Design – the case of the Rio Madeira HVDC Transmission System, Brazil

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Abstract

The two ground electrodes of the south end of the Rio Madeira HVDC transmission system are located within the volcanic-covered Paraná basin, SE Brazil. In this paper, we describe an upgrade in the methodology applied for the development of the 1D geoelectric model for the Bipole I south electrode site, and for the final adjustment of this model, based on the commissioning data. The preliminary model is based on data acquired with shallow (electroresistivity) and deep (magnetotelluric) geophysical soundings. Both soundings are affected by distortions caused by galvanic deviations, due to local surficial inhomogeneities, which produce a constant vertical deviation in the log-space of the whole apparent resistivity curves. For the development of the design geoelectric model, a first adjustment of the set of apparent resistivity curves is applied. After the electrode's commissioning an iterative calculation is applied for the simultaneous adjustment of the electrode resistance and of the geoelectric model.

1. Introduction

An HVDC energy transmission system comprises two converter stations interconnected by an HVDC - High Voltage Direct Current transmission system. Ground electrodes of HVDC transmission systems provide a low resistance current return path during both monopolar and bipolar operation, using the earth as the conductive medium. Each converter station is connected to its electrode through the “electrode line”. The electrode is a buried structure, designed for the injection of continuous currents into the ground. It has two basic operational modes – normal operation, in which the unbalance

current of the two poles of the HVDC transmission line is continuously injected into the ground, up to a few tens of Amperes; and the monopolar operation, in case of loss of one of the poles of the HVDC transmission line, which may have metallic return or ground return. In the case of a ground return, for short periods (a few hours), the electrode may be used to inject in the ground the overload current of the line, up to a few kiloamperes.

The Rio Madeira HVDC system crosses 2375 km in the central region of South America, connecting the two hydropower plants on the Madeira River (South Amazon Craton, NW Brazil) to the main consuming areas in SE Brazil. This system is composed of two ± 600 kV bipolar HVDC transmission systems (Bipoles I and II) interconnecting the converter stations of Porto Velho (NW Brazil) and Araraquara (SE Brazil). Each converter station has two grounding electrodes, one for each bipole HVDC transmission system, which makes possible the continuity of the power transmission, with ground return, in the case of loss of one of the poles of the DC line. The south electrode of the Bipole I is located 34 km away from the Araraquara Converter Substation and 26 km away from Gasbol, the Bolivia-Brazil gas pipeline.

The design of an HVDC ground electrode is a multidisciplinary activity, based on knowledge of electrical engineering and geosciences. The location of the electrode shall be carefully selected, to minimize the interferences in third-party-owned facilities near to it, due to the dissipation of such high DC currents in the ground from the electrode. As part of the electrode design, a regional geoelectric model allows for the calculation of the electrode electrical performance including the

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electrode resistance and the soil surface potential profile. The latter is used for the determination of the interference levels that may occur within the electrode interference area. Therefore, the first activity of the HVDC electrode design is the Site Selection, which searches within a few tens of kilometers around the Converter Substation for the site with the best geoelectric structure for hosting the ground electrode.

For the design of the South electrode of bipole I, a preliminary 1D geoelectric model was created, based on data acquired with shallow (electroresistivity) and deep (magnetotelluric) geophysical soundings. This model was assumed to be locally representative of the ground where the electrode is buried, and regionally representative of the deeper subsurface layers, within a radius of a few tens of km around the electrode. Induction logging of two test holes drilled within the electrode site was used for the shallow model calibration.

After the electrode construction, during the commissioning tests, the dc resistance of the electrode was measured with an auxiliary remote electrode, buried 11 km away from the main electrode, along the electrode line.

The measured resistance (0.052 Ω) was higher than the design value (0.037 Ω). The difference between the calculated and measured resistances was attributed mainly to static-shift effects on the MT data measured for the electrode site selection. Besides this finding, an additional upward adjustment of the measured resistance was needed, since the auxiliary electrode used in this measurement was not at the “remote earth”, that means not away enough to be out of the electrode influence.

This paper presents an upgrade of the methodology applied by the same authors [1] for developing the preliminary 1D geoelectric model of the site where it is located the south electrode of Bipole I, to be used for the electrode design, and then for the final adjustment of this model, with the elimination of the deviations caused by the static-shift, considering the restrictions of the fall-of-potential method for the measurement of the electrode resistance. The final correction of the geoelectric model is done employing an iterative process, which adjusts the geoelectric model to match the calculated and measured electrode performances. The adjustment is done simultaneously on the static-shift of the MT sounding and in the measured electrode resistance.

1.1 Geoelectric models and hvdc electrode simulation

The geoelectric structure of the ground can be modeled with different levels of complexity:

- homogeneous model – the same resistivity in all the subsurface volume;
- orthotropic (1D) model - the same resistivity is observed in each ground layer (horizontal and parallel strata);
- anisotropic model - resistivity variations are observed along two or three axes (2D or 3D).

The kind of geoelectric modeling to be adopted for the electrode project depends on the available geophysical data and on the software that will be used for the simulation of the electrode, which usually works with one of the following modeling methods – Finite-elements Method, which allows for the simulation of complex subsurface structures (3D models); or the Methods of Images and of the Moments, which allows for the modeling of specific ground structures (horizontally or vertically layered, concentric hemispheres etc.) [2]. Both methods are low-frequency (Lf) methods, so-named because they solve Maxwell’s Equations with no implicit approximations; however, the two methods differ fundamentally in the way the boundary conditions are imposed [3].

Each kind of modeling has its advantages and disadvantages. The 1D geoelectric model considers the geologic strata horizontal and parallel, being a model usually associated with specific geologic frameworks, such as sedimentary basins [4]. This model is the traditional option of the electrical engineering community for the simulation of grounding systems, allowing for the calculation of grounding grid electrical performance. Concerning the HVDC ground electrode, the 1D model allows for the calculation of its main electrical parameter, which is the resistance, an isotropic parameter that is not dependent on the direction taken for its measurement.

The other important performance parameter - the soil surface potential profile, is anisotropic and may vary according to the direction of the profile measurement. The use of a 1D model for the design of HVDC electrodes located within a 2D or 3D subsurface structure will result in circular soil surface equipotential, which will represent an “average” of the asymmetric equipotential associated to the actual subsurface structure. Besides its

Figure 1 - Geological map of the Araraquara area in the northeastern Paraná basin, SE Brazil [6]
Inset shows the study area (black rectangle) within the Paraná Basin (PB) in SE Brazil and contiguous countries.

simplicity, a good estimate of the regional 1D geoelectric model may be useful as the initial guess (starting model) for the 2D/3D inversion [5].

Three-dimensional (3D) inversion is possible, at least to some extent, depending on whether the resistivity survey covers a sufficiently wide area, with stations spacing compatible with the smallest scale targets. In practice, however, due to limitations on the number of sounding stations and unknown subsurface structures, it will be usually difficult to plan the resistivity survey to satisfy the desirable condition of 3D modeling. Often the stations spacing will be larger than the typical scale of the near-surface lateral heterogeneities, especially if the area is of complex geology.

The finite elements software is powerful for modeling wide volumes of ground, with dimensions of tens of kilometers, as required for HVDC grounding electrodes; however the generation of the model is complex and the time required for each simulation may be too long, depending on the hardware available. Besides these restrictions, a 3D geoelectric model requires a volume of data usually not compatible with the time and budget available for the geophysical surveys developed for the HVDC grounding electrode design, at least in Brazil.

Due to the above reasons, the geoelectric model applied for the design of all HVDC ground electrodes in Brazil is the 1D model, which allows for an estimate of the electrode resistance and the average soil surface potential profile. Due to the approximations required for this kind of modeling, in case of a 3D subsurface, the 1D model will be not good for inferring the maximum potential gradients close to the electrode perimeter or the asymmetric distribution of currents between sub-electrodes.

2. Site geology and geophysical surveys

The study area is located in the northeastern part of the Paraná basin (Figure 1), which is positioned on the southeastern South American Platform. The Bipole I electrode is positioned over the Adamantina Formation (Bauru Group), consisting of a thin layer of eolic sandstones resting over the basaltic flows of the Serra Geral Formation. During 2010-2011, a geophysical survey was carried out in this region, with regional broadband MT soundings at six stations. A concentrated study was developed within the selected site for this electrode, consisting of an extensive electroresistivity survey with 65 Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) and induction logging at two boreholes.

Figure 1 shows the location of the MT soundings and relevant converter station facilities over a schematic geologic map with the locations of MT stations (black triangles), converter substation (red square), ground electrodes (red circles identified for electrodes I and II) - geological periods of outcrops are CZ - Cenozoic cover; K - post-volcanic Late Cretaceous sediments; EK - Early Cretaceous volcanic; TC - pre-volcanic Triassic-Carboniferous sediments. It is also indicated the paths of the main Gasbol pipeline (thick blue line) and of its secondary pipelines (thin blue lines) that feed local towns. The red dot over the main Gasbol pipeline indicates the point where it was measured the pipe-to-ground potential, during the electrode commissioning (the closest point to the electrode location).

3. Deep surveys – MT Soundings

The magnetotelluric method (MT) is a geophysical technique for probing the deep Earth, from a few

Figure 2 - Unrotated MT curves from a sounding nearby the Electrode I site (Arq005) - apparent resistivity and phases from the electric dipole oriented at N20°W (squares), N70°E (triangles) and rotationally invariant (circles).

kilometers deep down to tens of kilometers. The MT method is based on the measurement of natural time-varying electromagnetic fields induced in the Earth's crust and mantle by atmospheric and ionospheric phenomena [7]. The time-series of the electrical and magnetic fields are measured at the soil surface in two orthogonal directions. The processing of this data results in two pairs of apparent resistivity and phase curves, which are inverted for obtaining a 2D model of the subsurface structure.

For this study, the time-series data of the horizontal components of the electric field (E_x and E_y) and of the horizontal and vertical components of the magnetic field (H_x , H_y and H_z) were recorded by a commercial single-station MT system (Metronix ADU-06). Recording time at each station was at least 2 days. The processing of this data with robust techniques resulted in reliable MT response function estimates in the period range of 0.0001s to 205s. Figure 2 illustrates the apparent resistivity and phase responses in the two measurement directions for the site nearly coincident with the position of the Electrode I (see Figure 1).

A common problem in studying the distribution of the electric conductivity in the Earth's crust is the static-shift effect [8, 9]. This effect is a consequence of small-scale near-surface structures, which are too small to have an inductive response at the highest frequency measured, however, distorting the electric field lines in the subsurface, introducing deviations on the measured soil surface electric field, which appear as a vertical shifting of the apparent resistivity curves. In magnetotelluric (MT) transfer functions, the vertical shifting of the apparent resistivity curve occurs by a frequency-independent factor, without any corresponding change in the phase curve. This effect is especially common in volcanic environments, where there can be large

changes in resistivity over short horizontal distances due to igneous intrusions and the varied resistivity of lava flows. Correction for static-shift is important because it introduces deviations in the apparent resistivity curves, affecting the calculated subsurface structure.

4. Shallow surveys

The electroresistivity survey was carried out using a DC resistivity-meter with a Schlumberger electrode arrangement. Within the Electrode I site, a total of 62 soundings were done along the previewed electrode perimeter, with maximum current electrodes separation up to 100 m, plus 3 additional soundings with separation up to 1000 m.

An average apparent resistivity curve as a function of electrode spacing was computed through the geometric mean of all apparent resistivity measured at each separation spacing. This averaging procedure considers that the static-shifts of the VES soundings present a normal distribution in the log-space [10], and thus, the geometric average of a large number of soundings allows for a significant reduction of the mean deviation. The upward tail of the apparent resistivity curve (for $AB/2 > 100$ m) is expected to characterize the basalt layer with higher resistivity, however, it does not have the same statistical validity of the preceding downward segment, because it is resultant of the average of only three wide-opening VES, besides being located in the tail of the curve, characterized by a low accuracy.

The two monitoring wells (T2B and T7B) were drilled at the higher and lower elevations along the previewed electrode perimeter, down to 50 m and 30 m, reaching the altered basalts of the Serra Geral layer. The water table was identified 6 m depth in well T2B and 2 m depth in the well T7B. Figure 3 presents the results of borehole logging, showing the gamma rays and resistivity profiles

Figure 3 - Gamma-ray and resistivity logging at two boreholes drilled at the higher elevation (red) and at the lower elevation (black), leveled accordingly to the conductive layer above the basalt layer (35 m depth in the graph).

of the two wells, side by side, leveled by the sandy/silty very conductive layer ($< 10 \Omega\text{m}$), which is common to the two wells and located a few meters above the basaltic layer.

The gamma-ray logging does not glean any information regarding resistivity; however, it helps the interpretation between different soil/rock types. The peaks of the gamma rays, above 100 API, can be associated with the presence of shales, justifying the higher conductivity of the common low resistivity layer.

Both wells present a high-resistivity first layer of a dry and lateritic ground of about 7 m deep, which saturated the induction probe due to the presence of thin iron-formation lenses. The deeper well reaches the lower resistivity layer below 23 m deep and the shallower well below 11 m deep. The well drilled at the higher elevation shows two low resistivity layers (100 Ωm and 20 Ωm), whereas the well at the lower elevation shows only the lower resistivity layer.

The basalt layer, which saturates the resistivity probe, appears about 42 m depth in the higher elevation well and 20 m depth in the lower elevation well. The undulated soil surface within the site presents an elevation difference of about 20 m. The difference between the depths of the basalt layer in the two wells is consistent with the elevation difference of the soil surface within the site, indicating that the top surface of the basalt is fairly flat in the site.

5. Geoelectric modeling

During the design phase of the electrode project, the available geophysical and geotechnical data were used

to produce a first-approach geoelectric model, which is used for the simulation of the electrode and calculation of its electrical performance (resistance and soil surface potential profile). More details on the data can be found in Freire [11].

5.1 Shallow Ground Geoelectric Modeling

IPI2Win software [12] was used for the inversion of the VES average apparent resistivity curve, which was done under the constraint of the data acquired by the induction logging, adjusted for an intermediate basalt layer average depth between the two wells, as illustrated in Figure 4.

The average depth for the Bauru Formation layer in the model resulted in higher than the simple average of the basalt top at the two wells, which can be explained by the fact that the average model is affected by the higher volume of the sandstones of the Northeast portion of the site, closer to the higher elevation well T2B.

Five layers are interpreted for this shallow geoelectric model, starting with a 1 m layer of 410 Ωm , interpreted as thin and dry topsoil with organic material. The topsoil is underlined by a high-resistivity dry layer (1000 $\Omega\text{m} \times 4 \text{ m}$), consisting of a well-drained alluvial sandy-clay subsoil with lateritic lenses. The third layer (120 $\Omega\text{m} \times 17 \text{ m}$) corresponds to the water-saturated sandstones of the Bauru Formation and the fourth layer is a mix of the sandstones of the lower Bauru formation with the altered basalts of the top of the Serra Geral Formation.

The last ascending segment of the apparent resistivity curve, with half current electrode spacing ($AB/2$) from 100 m to 500 m, indicates the influence of the basalts of the Serra Geral Formation. This last layer of the shallow model is not well defined, because it was inferred from

Figure 4 - Average VES data within Electrode I site and corresponding five-layer model (RMS error < 4%) - open circles are the VES data, red line the fitted curve and blue line the inverted resistivity model; table with the average shallow geoelectric model, with resistivity (ρ) in Ωm , and layer width (h) and layer bottom depth (d) in meters.

the last segment of the apparent resistivity curve, which indicates the trend of increasing resistivity by only three wide soundings. The resistivity of the Serra Geral basalts, about 140 m thick at Araraquara, will be better defined by the inversion of the MT data, constrained by the shallow model.

5.2 first-approach adjustment of the mt curves

Berdichevsky [7] suggested that an average regional 1D model of the geoelectric structure of an area could be calculated using the geometric average of the invariants of the MT impedances retrieved from a large number of soundings in the area under study. MT soundings are based on the measurement of electric fields on the soil surface that can be affected by galvanic deviations due to heterogeneities in the resistivity of shallow ground layers, which introduce distortions in the MT impedance matrices. These deviations are not random and therefore are not associated with a Gaussian distribution of errors, resulting in invariants of the apparent resistivity curves of the regional MT survey that are displaced upward or downward (more often downward) by different factors, which are constant in the log-log scale for each curve [13]. This means that, in general, the invariant of the apparent resistivity curves (1D) of different MT stations present lower values than the real ones, which results in an average 1D regional model more conductive than the real one [14].

The processing of the MT apparent resistivity and phases curves included the following activities:

- production of the 1D curves for each sounding station, with the calculation of the averages of the XY and YX curves – geometric average for the apparent resistivity and arithmetic average for the phases (an approximation of the invariant MT curves at the surveyed stations);
- elimination of the segments of the apparent resistivity and phase curves that diverge from the main trend, taking the healthy curves as references [15];

- preliminary adjustment of the static distortions of the MT average curves, according to the methodology proposed in Chapter 11.1 of Berdichevsky & Dmitriev [16];
- inversion of the set of adjusted apparent resistivity and phase curves constrained by the expected depth of the basement in Araraquara, about 2 km deep.

Figure 5 presents the 1D invariants of the apparent resistivity and phases of the six MT stations (MT Station 5 is the one close to electrode 1 site), which were processed for a preliminary adjustment of the static distortions. Berdichevsky and Dmitriev [16] suggest a simple rule for static-shift correction – the apparent resistivity curves should be corrected for the static-shift at periods with coincident phases at the adjacent sites.

For the case here studied, the authors identified the so-called ρ -effect, which are static distortions caused by near-surface resistivity inhomogeneities, occurring over the entire frequency range of the apparent resistivity curves, including the upper layers and substratum. Using the phase indication in Figure 5, it is possible to observe that period $T_s = 0.8$ s marks the boundary between the zones with divergent (higher frequencies) and convergent (lower frequencies) phase curves. The analysis of these graphics shows that between periods 0.8s to 10s, the phases of the MT curves overlap (except for stations Arq002 and Arq004, which present distortions), while the corresponding apparent resistivity average curves are scattered in the vertical axis. It is considered that the phases of the MT curves do not overlap to the end of the curve because the tails of the curves are affected by higher levels of noise.

Figure 6 illustrates the MT average curves, which were submitted to two adjustments. The first adjustment, before the data interpretation, was the removal of the segments interpreted as corrupted responses, as suggested by Padilha et al. [15] - Arq004 was eliminated and the tail segments of the curves of stations Arq001

Figure 5 - MT 1D average apparent resistivity and phases x period (s) curves sounded by INPE.

Figure 6 - MT 1D apparent resistivity and phases x period (s) curves adjusted for the ρ -effect static distortion.

(from period 12.8 s) and Arq002 (from period 0.8 s) were discarded, due to their significant deviations from the main trend defined by the soundings Arq003, Arq005 and Arq006. The second adjustment was done with the application of a multiplicative constant over the entire period range, calculated for each apparent resistivity curve, to have all five curves coincident with the value of 30 Ωm at period 0.8 s (Table I). This multiplicative constant for each curve was defined by the ratio of the selected value to the original apparent resistivity at the corresponding period, considering that the sum of the natural logarithms of the static-shifts of the set of curves should sum to zero [13]. The phase curves remained unaltered.

Table I - First-approach Static-shift Adjustment Factor for the MT Apparent Resistivity Curves.

MT Station	Arq001	Arq002	Arq003	Arq005	Arq006
Adjustment Factor	0.95	1.00	0.76	1.52	0.90

The resultant upward and overlapping tails of the curves were considered representative of the regional basement, at the depth of about 2.3 km, calculated from an apparent resistivity of 30 Ωm at period 0.8 s, which is consistent with the expected basement depth at Araraquara [17]. This first-approach adjustment of the static deviations of the set of MT curves considers that the regional crystalline basement is common for the area

surveyed by the MT stations, and therefore the tails of the average MT apparent resistivity curves are expected to be common to the different curves of the MT dataset. This procedure was applied considering the following premises:

- the regionality of the MT survey is characterized by the proximity of the MT stations, within a radius below 20 km, and located within the same tectonic setting;
- the 1D inherent characteristic of a deep sedimentary basin, with the maximum sounding period around 100 s, where the 1D premise is still a reasonable approximation;
- the inversion of the adjusted MT curves with good data quality (Arq01, Arq05 and Arq06) shows similar geoelectric structures for the MT stations.

The spatial adjustment applied uses only intrinsic information from the MT dataset, which may allow for achieving a relative adjustment between the available apparent resistivity curves, but not resulting in an absolute static-shift correction of each curve, because the entire dataset is usually downward biased [13]. Besides the premise that the shift factors present a Gaussian distribution around zero, which is an approximation, the statistical approach will not hold for the typical HVDC electrode Site Selection, where the number of MT stations will rarely be statistically relevant, being usually limited between 6 to 12 MT stations. For these

Figure 7 - First-order adjusted MT curves (black, $\Omega\text{m} \times \text{period}/\text{depth}$), and calculated (red) with the corresponding 1D geoelectric model (blue line and table), constrained by the shallow model (RMS error < 5%).

reasons the first-approach methodology results only in a relative adjustment of the static deviations of the set of MT curves, allowing for the comparison of the geoelectric structure of the sites and for the selection of the best one to host the electrode.

The coherence between the geoelectric models obtained from the inversion of the adjusted MT curves for stations Arq01, Arq05 and Arq06, which revealed basement depths between 2.3 km and 2.4 km, shows that the adjustment applied established a common regional basement for the set of MT soundings. The proposed method is easily applied and is practical for the typical MT survey for HVDC electrode site selection.

5.3 First-approach Geoelectric Model

To allow for the verification of the data integration from both sounding techniques, the VES apparent resistivity data were transformed into frequency (period) domain by using the empirical scaling relationship proposed by Meju [18]. Figure 10 presents the average apparent resistivity curves of the VES (orange) and adjusted MT station Arq005 (blue), which reveal some discordance between the upward segments of the two curves around period 0.001 s.

The first-approach adjusted MT apparent resistivity and phase curves of station Arq005 were inverted under the constraint of the shallow geoelectric model previously determined by the inversion of the VES average apparent resistivity curve (disregarding the basement layer). Figure 7 presents the calculated curves (red) with the corresponding 1D geoelectric model (blue line and table).

Table II - Interpretation of the first-approach 1D geoelectric model. presents the interpretation of the 1D geoelectric model of the site, which is quite compatible with the known stratigraphic layers of the Paraná Sedimentary Basin in Araraquara. The first three layers, retrieved from the shallow geoelectric model, can be associated with the Cenozoic cover and the Cretaceous Bauru Group sandstones. The transition between the two geophysical methods (VES and MT) occurs in the fourth layer, which includes the transition of the bottom of the Bauru sandstones and the basalts on the top of the Serra Geral Formation.

The total thickness of the basalt layer is expected to be around 150-200 m, according to water wells drilled in the area. However, the geophysical soundings were

Table II - Interpretation of the first-approach 1D geoelectric model.

Layer No	Layer Description	Resistivity (Ωm)	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)
1	Topsoil with organic matter	410	1	1
2	Dry sandy ground above the water table (Bauru Fm.)	1000	4	5
3	Water saturated sandy soils (Bauru Fm.)	120	13	18
4	Bauru Fm. and top of Serra Geral Fm.	18	50	68
5	Serra Geral + Botucatu + Pirambóia Formations	80	700	768
6	Aquifers substrate (Groups Passa Dois and Tubarão)	22	1500	2270
7	Crystalline Basement	600		

Figure 8 - Electrode I configuration as reproduced by the software CDEGS, 3D view (a) and top view (b) with the indication of the N (Y-axis) and NW (corner) directions.

not able to distinguish the two water-saturated ground layers – the bottom of the fractured basalts and the sandstones below it. The fifth layer is thus representative of the Jurassic-Cretaceous São Bento Group, including the lower part of the Serra Geral Formation and the sandstones of the Pirambóia-Botucatu succession, which yield the same resistivity ($80 \Omega\text{m} \times 700 \text{ m}$). The sixth layer of low resistivity ($22 \Omega\text{m} \times 1500 \text{ m}$), can be associated with the Carboniferous-Permian Passa Dois (marine sediments) and Tubarão (glacial and postglacial sediments) Groups, which lie directly on top of about 2.3 km deep fractured crystalline basement, a depth compatible with the expected basement at Araraquara, about 2 km depth.

Considering the data available for the electrode design, this would be the model to be used for the simulation of the electrode to calculate its design performance. The first minimum of the MT curve is much lower than the first minimum of the VES curve (see Figure 7), an indication that probably the average MT apparent resistivity curve is still affected by a downward static deviation and, therefore, deserves some complimentary adjustment.

5.4 Electrode Simulation

Electrode 1 in Araraquara is a semi-double vertical ring, occupying an approximately rectangular area of about $820 \times 560 \text{ m}$ (external perimeter with 2636 m). It comprises 160 wells with different depths - 20 m (74 wells), 30 m (50 wells) and 40 m (36 wells), due to the undulated topography of the Bauru Formation above the flat top of the Serra Geral Formation (Cretaceous basalts) as shown in Figure 8.

To be consistent with the 1D geoelectric model, which approaches the undulated soil surface by a flat plane, the 160 wells with different depths according to its elevation, were averaged weighted by its lengths, resulting in an equivalent 27,6 m well. Considering that the electrode was built with PVC pipes down to 5 m and then with

steel pipes down to the bottom of the well, the modeled average electrode is composed of 160 equivalent wells, each with a steel pipe ($\varnothing 350 \text{ mm}$) starting at 5 m depth and extending down to 27.6 m.

The simulation of the average electrode configuration using the geoelectric model of Table I was carried out using the software CDEGS and resulted in a design ground resistance of 0.038Ω .

6. Final Geoelectric Model Adjustment

Among the commissioning tests in the Araraquara Bipole I electrode, conducted by different companies and with different measurement protocols, three were selected for this analysis, which measured the electrode resistance, potential differences at the soil surface in the NW direction (see Figure 8b) and pipe-to-ground potential at the Gasbol pipeline. The premise for the adjustment of the geoelectric model considers that the calculated and measured electrode parameters should match.

6.1 Electrode Commissioning Measurements

Figure 9 presents the measured electrode resistance curve, referenced to the nominal current of 2625 A. This survey was done with the electrode line grounded with an auxiliary electrode, buried in a swampy area about 11 km from the electrode, and energized by a rotating welding machine, which injected 21.5 A in the electrode. The resistance to the remote ground was calculated with the Fall of Potential Method, by measuring the potential between the busbar in the Switching House (in the center of the electrode), and a moving rod that was displaced away from the electrode center in steps of 25 m, 50 m or 100 m. At the distance of 1800 m, the potential difference between the local ground and the busbar in the electrode center seemed to stabilize around 1.13 V, and the survey was interrupted. The electrode resistance of 0.053Ω was calculated through the ratio of this potential by the injected current of 21.5 A.

Figure 9 - Measured resistance x distance curve and 2nd order polynomial trend, from the center of electrode 1 [11].

The 2nd order polynomial trend calculated for the resistance curve shows that at 1.8 km distance, the resistance curve still shows an upward trend, meaning that the “remote ground”, a place far enough from the electrode where its interference is not perceptible, has not been reached yet. The measured resistance of 0,053 Ω, besides being a partial value that does not represent the actual electrode resistance, is about 40% higher than the design electrode resistance (0.038 Ω), calculated with the geoelectric model built from inversion of the first-approach adjusted curve of MT station Arq005. The mismatch between the measured and calculated resistances indicates that the design geoelectric model still needs an adjustment, to allow for the correct calculation of the electrode parameters.

The measurement of soil surface potential differences was carried out during the electrode commissioning tests with the complete HVDC system in monopolar operation with ground return and a current of 406 A. During this test,

potential differences on the soil surface were measured from the electrode center to 942 m away, along a radial line passing by the electrode NW corner - 25 m stretch up to 400 m, 50 m stretch from 400 m to 600 m, and 100 m stretch from 600 m to 900 m, with a final short stretch of 42 m at the end (Figure 10).

The pipe-to-ground potential at the Gasbol pipeline was measured at the monitoring point PT SP-133 (Table III - Measured pipe-to-ground potential at the Gasbol pipeline, at point PT SP-133, 26 km from the electrode center, for the monopolar operation with each pole outage.), the closest one to the electrode (26 km from its center). The potential was measured with the HVDC system in monopolar operation at both polarities (turning off first one of the poles and then the other). From the measured potentials, it was discounted the contribution of the pipe-to-ground potential applied by the cathodic protection system (measured just before each monopolar operation). The two potentials were then referenced to the nominal

Figure 10 – Soil surface potential differences from the electrode center to 942 m away, measured in the NW direction, referenced to the nominal electrode current (2625 A).

Table III - Measured pipe-to-ground potential at the Gasbol pipeline, at point PT SP-133, 26 km from the electrode center, for the monopolar operation with each pole outage.

Pole	Pipe-to-ground voltage before the current injection (V)	Injected Current (A)	Pipe-to-ground voltage after the current injection (V)	Net voltage variation (referenced to the bipole nominal current of 2625 A)
1	1.6 V	2850	1.79	$(1.79 + 1.6) \times 2625/2850 = 3.1 \text{ V}$
2	1.6 V	3156	4.85	$(4.85 - 1.6) \times 2625/3156 = 2.7 \text{ V}$

bipole current (2625 A) and averaged, resulting in the final mean pipe-to-ground potential of 2.9 V.

6.2 Final Adjustment

The final adjustment is done by an iterative processing method based on the theoretical soil surface potential profile, calculated from successive direct (forward) simulations of the electrode geometry with the geoelectric model. The simulations were done with successive adjustments of the geoelectric model until it was achieved a good match of the calculated and measured electrode electrical parameters.

Despite the geoelectric model is built from different geophysical data, being both VES and MT data subjected to the static-shift deviation, the difference between the measured and calculated electrode resistances was attributed only to the MT data. This is justified by the fact that only one MT sounding is available, whereas the shallow model is built from the average of many VES soundings, which was calibrated by the measured data of the wells profiling.

The total electrode resistance was calculated from the sum of the measured resistance at 1.8 km plus the residual resistance from this distance to the remote ground, which is extracted from the calculated soil surface potential profile. An interactive process was applied for a simultaneous adjustment of the two parameters (the geoelectric model and the electrode resistance).

This process uses the software (CDEGS) for the simulation of the injection of the bipole nominal current (2625 A) into the electrode and iteratively adjusts the geoelectric model according to the following steps:

- apply an arbitrary upward scale factor to the MT apparent resistivity curve and then invert the adjusted MT curves under the constraint of the available shallow model;
- perform simulation of the electrode (with CDEGS), using the adjusted geoelectric model and injecting the nominal current, for the calculation of its resistance and ground potential at the measuring distance (1.8 km);
- divide the ground potential (in Volts) at the measuring distance (1.8 km) by the injected current to obtain

Figure 11 - VES apparent resistivity curve (blue) with spacings converted to period [18], original MT curve at station Arq001 (yellow), first-approach adjusted average MT curve with 1.52 scale factor (brown), and final adjustment of the MT curve (red) with the application of an additional 1.52 scale factor (total scale factor of 2.31).

Figure 12 - Final adjusted MT curves (black, $\Omega\text{m} \times \text{period/depth}$), and calculated (red) with the corresponding 1D geoelectric model (blue line and table), constrained by the shallow model.

- the residual resistance, which is the fraction of the electrode resistance from the measuring point (1.8 km) to the remote ground, and add this calculated complementary resistance to the measured value (0,053 Ω) to obtain the adjusted electrode resistance;
- compare the resistances calculated by CDEGS and adjusted (measured + calculated residual) – if they match it means that the final geoelectric model was achieved, otherwise the procedure shall be restarted, vertically adjusting the MT apparent resistivity curve with a new scale factor.

Applying the iterative calculations above summarized, a final MT apparent resistivity curve was achieved as shown in Figure 11, adjusted by an additional 1.52 scale factor, which was inverted under the constraint of the shallow ground model, resulting in the final geoelectric model of Figure 12, interpreted in Table IV.

The geoelectric layers of the final model are compatible with the known stratigraphic layers of this region. The first three layers can be associated with the Cenozoic cover and Cretaceous Bauru Group sandstones and are quite compatible with the results of the wells profiling. The fourth layer represents the transition between the sandstones of the Bauru Group and the basalts of the Serra Geral Formation (27 x 53 m). The fifth layer is representative of the Jurassic-Cretaceous São Bento Group, including the lower part of the Serra Geral

Formation and the sandstones of the Pirambóia-Botucatu succession (110 $\Omega\text{m} \times 1000$ m). The sixth low-resistivity layer (30 $\Omega\text{m} \times 1600$ m) can be associated with the Carboniferous-Permian Passa Dois (marine sediments) and Tubarão (glacial and postglacial sediments) Groups, which lie directly on top of the fractured crystalline basement (800 Ωm).

The simulation with this final geoelectric model resulted in the electrode resistance of 0.058 Ω , with the ground potential of 22 V at 1.8 km for a current injection of 2625 A. The residual resistance from 1.8 km away can be thus calculated:

- $R_r = V(1.8 \text{ km}) / I_n = 22/2625 = 0.008 \Omega$.

Adding the above calculated residual resistance to the measured Electrode I resistance at 1.8 km results nearly on the same resistance calculated by the simulation (mismatch < 2%):

- $R = 0.053 + 0.008 = 0.061 \Omega$.

Figure 13 presents the calculated soil surface potential curves in two directions - N (yellow) and NW (red), referenced to the nominal current of 2625 A, and the measured curve (blue). The latter is the segment of the potential differences measured outside the electrode perimeter (last upward segment of Figure 10), which was vertically inverted and adjusted to fit in the corresponding calculated curve (NW). This vertical adjustment was

Table IV - Interpretation of the final 1D geoelectric model.

Layer No	Layer Description	Resistivity (Ωm)	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)
1	topsoil with organic matter	410	1	-
2	sandy and dry ground above the water table (Bauru Fm.)	1000	4	5
3	water-saturated sandy soil (Bauru Fm.)	120	17	22
4	Bauru Fm and top of Serra Geral Fm.	27	53	75
5	Serra Geral + Botucatu + Pirambóia Formations	110	1000	1080
6	Aquifers Substrate (Groups Passa Dois and Tubarão)	30	1600	~ 2700
7	Basement	800	∞	

Figure 13 - Calculated soil surface potential curves in two directions - N (yellow) and NW (red), according to Figure 8; and measured potential gradients in the NW direction (blue), referenced to the nominal current of 2625 A.

needed because the original set of data is a series of potential differences measured at the soil surface with no reference to the remote ground. The adjusted blue segment of the measured curve overlaps the calculated red curve, both for the NW direction, indicating that the measured and calculated soil surface potential gradients match well, despite the approximations of the model (1D geoelectric model and averaged wells). The effect of the asymmetric electrode perimeter on the soil surface potential profiles is limited to less than a 2-km radius.

The potential calculated at 26 km is 2.7 V, a good result since the average measured pipe-to-ground potential at the GASBOL pipeline at the same distance was 2.9 V. The differences between these two potentials can be attributed to a local superposition of effects because the pipe potential is affected not only by the main pipeline but also by the potentials of the two secondary pipelines that attend the neighboring cities.

7. Conclusions

This paper presents the methodology applied for the estimation of the geoelectric model for the site of an HVDC ground electrode, located in a sedimentary basin, within a predominantly 1D-layered ground structure. The proposed method applies to the electrode design and commissioning phases, successively adjusting the static-shift of the MT soundings with the available data. For the final geoelectric model, adjusted based in the electrode commissioning data, it shall be highlighted the following findings:

- the measured resistance with the fall-of-potential method is a partial value that does not represent the actual electrode resistance since it is not practical to reach the “remote earth” during the commissioning tests, therefore a complimentary adjustment of this parameter was needed, what was achieved

simultaneously to the adjustment of the 1D geoelectric model;

- as a consequence or the above adjustment, a good match was obtained for the near-field, concerning the measured and calculated soil surface potential gradients in the NW direction, and for the far-field, associated with the measured and calculated pipe-to-ground potential 26 km away from the electrode.

This good match, despite the approximations of the 1D model and averaged wells, can be attributed to the fact that the regional tectonic setting is a sedimentary basin, therefore compatible with the 1D geoelectric model.

The proposed adjustment is based on the premise that the average 1D invariants of the MT curves are downward biased, therefore it is suggested the application of a preliminary upward correction of the corresponding apparent resistivity curve at the electrode site, early in the electrode design phase. Considering that the average shallow apparent resistivity curve was coherent with the well’s profiling, the multiplying factor was applied to the MT apparent resistivity curve, allowing for a better fit of the shallow and deep apparent resistivity curves in the transition range.

Figure 14 presents the two Schlumberger average apparent resistivity curves, with the transition layer adjusted between the two sets of curves (shallow and deep) – first-approach adjusted (x 1.52) and final adjustment (x 2.31). It can be observed that the upward factor of 2.31 applied to the invariant of the MT sounding at the electrode 1 site allowed for a better adjustment of the transition ground layer between the shallow and MT apparent resistivity curves.

The adjustment of the transition ground layer between the two apparent resistivity curves is an important achievement because this layer is not well defined in the

Figure 14 - Schlumberger average apparent resistivity, with the transition layer (last layer) adjusted between the two sets of curves (shallow and deep) – MT first approach adjusted (x 1.52) and final adjustment (x 2.31).

tail of the shallow average curve neither for the higher frequencies of the MT invariant, were both sounding methods loose accuracy. This shallow layer, because it is still close to the electrode, is important in the definition of its electrical performance (resistance and soil surface potential profile) within a few km of the electrode.

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9. Biographies

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